

Towards explanation strategies in group recommender systems

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Abstract—Explanation has becoming a necessary issue in current intelligent systems. Particularly, in the scenario of recommender systems several research works have been focused on explaining the rationality behind the generated recommendations. Such explanations have been developed under two different paradigms: 1) the intrinsic explanations focused on explaining the recommendation procedure, or 2) the post-hoc explanations, focused on explaining the recommendation output. However, most of the research done in this direction is focused on individual recommendation. In contrast, the current contribution is dedicated to screening the post-hoc recommendation explanation paradigm in group recommender systems.

Keywords—group recommendation; post-hoc explanation; association rules

I. MOTIVATION

Recommender systems (RSs) are AI-based applications focused on providing users with the information that best fits their preferences and needs in overloaded search spaces [1]. Particularly, group recommender systems have been centered in those RS scenarios where the items are consumed in groups, such as TV programs and travel packages, and not individually [2].

In this way, recommendation explanation has become a necessary research area in order to promote the recommendation trustworthiness. Some key works have been developed with this purpose in mind, specifically focused on post-hoc explanations. For example, Peake and Wang [3] have presented the explanation mining post-hoc approach, that uses association rule mining for finding relationships between the user preferences and the recommendation output, using such information for explaining the generated recommendations. Shmaryahu et al. [4], in a different direction, use simply-to-explain, basic recommendation algorithms, as base for explaining more complex approaches such as matrix factorization-based.

However, as far as it can be identified by recent works and literature analyses on explaining recommendation output [3, 4, 5], there is a lack of works focused on group recommender systems. A recent work, developed by Barile et al. [6], has been focused in this direction, but it has been mainly centered on evaluating explainable social choice-based aggregation strategies, instead of exploring approaches that can be used

across different group recommendation approaches, such as post-hoc approaches.

The current contribution is then focused on bringing the post-hoc explanation approach into the group recommendation context.

II. METHODOLOGY

Our initial approach focused on providing post-hoc explanations in group recommendation, contains two main stages:

- 1) The mining of association rules with the structure (A,B, C -> D) being A, B, C, D items, taking as base the individual user preferences data, as formerly proposed by Lin et al. [7].
- 2) The composing of group recommendation explanations, taking as base the discovered rules.

In the scope of the current work, two novel explanation types are considered, built over a rule such as (A,B,C -> D):

- Type I: “The item D is recommended because at least n members of the group preferred items A, B, and C”.
- Type II: “The item D is recommended because in the group all the members have preferred A, B, or C; and the three items have been preferred by at least one member”.

To formalize these explanation types, we assume an association rule with the format (I, j) , where the item set I represents the antecedent of the rule, and j the item in the consequent. Furthermore, let's be $I_u \in I$ the subset of the item set in the antecedent of the rule, containing items preferred by the user $u \in G$.

For the case of *Type I explanation*, a rule can be used for supporting this kind of explanations whether it satisfies the following condition for at least n users:

$$I = I_u$$

This is, that such users should prefer all the items in the antecedent of the rule I , for firing the Type I explanations associated to such rule.

For *Type II explanation*, a rule (I,j) can support it if it satisfies the following condition:

$$I = \bigcup_{u \in G} I_u$$

which means that the union of all the items in the subsets I_u , matches with the antecedent of the rule.

It is stated that in addition, it has to satisfy the second condition:

$$\forall_{u \in G} I \cap I_u \neq \emptyset$$

that means that all users u in the group, $u \in G$, should have at least some items that are also in the antecedent of the rule.

III. FINDINGS

An experimental protocol was done using the Movielens 100K dataset (<https://grouplens.org/datasets/movielens/100k/>), for evaluating the model fidelity [3] associated to explanations generated by both explanation types.

The model fidelity criterion has been widely used for characterizing the effectiveness of post-hoc explanations in several previous works [3], including our previous research work that serves as antecedent to the current proposal [8]. The model fidelity of an explainability approach is characterized as:

$$Fidelity(M) = \frac{|set\ of\ recommendal\ items \cap set\ of\ justifiable\ recommendations|}{|set\ of\ recommendal\ items|}$$

For the evaluation purpose, we construct multiple groups of a predetermined size. For composing these groups, we prioritize individuals with a significant rating correlation ($\alpha > 0.5$), a common criterion for building groups. Our attention is directed towards evaluating the existing proposals within small-sized groups, particularly those comprising 5 or 6 members for the Movielens dataset.

TABLE I
FIDELITY VALUES

Type I Explanations			
	n=1	n=3	n=4
Group size 5	0.78	0.71	0.23
Group size 6	0.71	0.66	0.45
Type II Explanations			
Group size 5	0.62		
Group size 6	0.59		

In this scenario, we generate a recommendation list tailored to each specific group by utilizing a group recommendation algorithm. Specifically, we adopt a preference aggregation-based recommendation approach [9], employing the traditional matrix factorization method for generating individual recommendations within the group [9], and utilizing the average as the aggregation approach.

Table I illustrates the results associated to our experimental setting. For the case of Type I explanations, we use $n=1$, $n=3$, and $n=4$, for number of users that have to satisfy the whole set of items at the antecedent of the association rule.

As could be expected, in the first type of GRS explanations, larger values of n leads to the reaching of a lower fidelity values. While for $n=1$ and $n=3$ the fidelity values lie around

0.7, for $n=4$ have a relevant decreasing up to 0.23 for group size 5 and up to 0.45 for size 6.

In a different direction, the second type of GRS explanations adds more flexibility to the explanation generation process. Specifically, it leads to a fidelity of 0.62 for group size 5 and 0.59 for group size 6. It is important to highlight that this performance is worse than the obtained by the first kind of explanations for $n=1$ and $n=3$, but better than the scenario $n=4$.

These results illustrates that each approach can be complemented each other.

IV. IMPLICATIONS AND VALUE

The current work presents, as far as we know, one of the primary efforts on exploring post-hoc explanation in group recommendations, being characterized by the model fidelity criteria. The promising results obtained by the performed evaluation, open some research avenues on screening further explanation types in this context, which can incorporate additional information such as the associated to item attributes. User studies for evaluating the acceptance of these explanation types can be further developed.

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